

Synergistic enzyme assisted release of ferulic acid from brewer's spent grain

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ABSTRACT

Brewer's spent grain (BSG), the most abundant by-product of the beer industry, can be considered a sustainable source of ferulic acid (4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamic acid) (FA). FA is esterified to the arabinoxylan in the BSG. FA exhibits a variety of biological activities and is a target for valorization of BSG. We present a novel enzyme-assisted approach that utilizes the synergistic action of a specific bacterial endo-1,4- β -xylanase and a fungal ferulic acid esterase activity to selectively release high yields of FA from BSG. The study compares the efficacy of three different fungal feruloyl esterases (E.C. 3.1.1.73) of carbohydrate esterase family 1 (CE1), *HfFae*, *AoFae1*, and *AnFae1*, acting separately or in combination with two different endo-1,4- β -xylanases (EC 3.2.1.8), a bacterial GH30 enzyme from *Dickeya chrysanthemi*, and Shearzyme®, a commercial GH10 enzyme from *Aspergillus aculeatus*, respectively. On an equimolar dosage basis, the *AnFae1*-GH30 was the most efficient combination in releasing FA from BSG. This combination showed significant synergy in a dose-dependent manner, enabling up to 85% FA recovery from BSG within 30 min. of treatment. The results demonstrate a novel enzymatic approach for valorization of BSG as FA is considered a high-value natural compound for use in e.g. anti-aging skin care products.

1. Introduction

Brewers' spent grain (BSG) is the insoluble solid residue left over from the mashing kettle in beer production after the saccharified starch is removed from the malted barley. It is the most abundant byproduct of the brewing process, representing 85% of the total brewing waste material [1] and around 20 kg of wet BSG are produced per 100 L of brewed beer [2,3]. At the current beer production levels [4], this means that ~36.4 million tons of BSG are generated globally per year [4,5].

BSG is rich in cellulose and hemicellulose, with the hemicellulose primarily consisting of substituted arabinoxylan, which can constitute up to 40% of the BSG on a dry matter basis. The arabinoxylan interacts with the cellulose fibrils through hydrogen bonding and can be covalently linked to lignin via the hydroxycinnamic acid groups [6,7]. The arabinoxylan is composed of β -(1,4)-linked xylopyranosyl residues forming the linear backbone of the polysaccharide. Arabinose residues are attached to the xylan backbone via α -(1,2) or α -(1,3) linked substitutions or sometimes both α -(1,2) and α -(1,3) on the same xylopyranosyl moiety. Alternatively, as in arabinoxylans from other types of grasses, some of the xylose residues may be acetylated at the O-2 and/or

O-3 positions or substituted with α -1,2-linked (4-O-methyl)-glucuronic acid (GlcA) [7]. Some of the arabinose residues may be esterified with a hydroxycinnamate, i.e. *trans*-ferulic acid (FA) or to a lesser extent *trans*-p-coumaric acid (p-Cu) at the O5 position. In barley arabinoxylan, and thus in the BSG, this esterification is primarily to FA (Fig. 1).

The substitutions, including both the extent of GlcA substitutions and esterification to FA and p-Cu confer different physico-chemical and structural properties to the arabinoxylan polymer, and provide for various functional interactions with other cell wall components, including cellulose and lignin [7–9]. The hydroxycinnamates can thus be esterified or etherified to lignin, and cross-linking of ferulates results in the formation of diferulic acid bridges that connect different arabinoxylan chains [9]. Currently, BSG is primarily used as animal feed, but its composition makes it suitable for a variety of value-added uses. The phenolic acid compounds, i.e. the hydroxycinnamates such as FA and p-coumaric acid, are of considerable interest to the society due to their putative health benefits [10,11].

Several methods have been developed to release ferulic acid from vegetable biomasses and agricultural residues [11]. Alkaline hydrolysis stands out as one of the most widely used for such release, mainly

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because alkali induces breakage of ester-linkages, and induces solubilization of lignin. However, disadvantages of this approach include the negative environmental impact as a result of the high chemical demand. Furthermore, the resultant hydrolysate is difficult to purify due to its alkalinity, and the non-specific action of the alkaline treatment causes the presence of degradation and condensation components, which appear as brown pigments.

Enzymatic hydrolysis has been investigated as a potentially feasible and sustainable method for releasing FA from complex arabinoxylan-rich streams, including BSG [11,12]. Enzymatic release offers several advantages, including high extraction yields, higher quality extracts, environmentally friendly extraction, scalability, and high selectivity as the correctly chosen enzymes can specifically target the ester bonds linking FA to the arabinoxylan without damaging other valuable compounds [13]. The selective enzymatic release of FA from arabinoxylans can be accomplished by feruloyl esterases (FAEs) (E.C. 3.1.1.73). This class of enzymes belongs to the carbohydrate esterase family 1 (CE1) according to the classification in the Carbohydrate-Active Enzymes Database (www.cazy.org) [14] and the FAEs catalyze the hydrolysis of ester bonds between ferulate and arabinofuranosyl moieties, releasing FA from arabinoxylan [11–13].

In the CAZy database more than 1000 putative fungal FAEs are classified into 13 subfamilies of CE1 based on prediction from genome mining and phylogenetic analysis [14–16].

The *Aspergillus niger* feruloyl esterase (FAE III), known as *AnFae* or *AnFae1*, is a classical representative of the CE1 family and was one of the first feruloyl esterases to be described [17]. This enzyme can catalyze the hydrolysis of the ester bond linking monomeric FA to arabinose in arabinoxylan, including in spent barley grains, and wheat bran, and early data show significantly enhanced FA release with a combined (or sequential) treatment of *AnFae1* and an endo-1,4- β -xylanase derived from *Trichoderma viride* [17]. Such improved release by enzymatic treatment with FAE and endo-1,4- β -xylanase has since been corroborated in other studies with different types of xylan substrates, including e.g. enhanced FAE-catalyzed release of FA from endo-1,4- β -xylanase-solubilized glucuronoarabinoxylan from corn bran [18, 19].

Endo-1,4- β -xylanases (EC 3.2.1.8) thus catalyze the hydrolysis of the β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-glycosidic linkages between xylose residues in the xylan backbone of arabinoxylans, resulting in the production of different substituted and unsubstituted xylo-oligosaccharides depending on the substrate, endo-1,4- β -xylanase type and enzyme specificity [9]. Endo-1,4- β -xylanases are classified into glycoside hydrolase (GH) families 5, 8, 10, 11, 30, 98, and 141 according to the gene sequences of their catalytic domain in CAZy [14], and notably families GH5, GH10, GH11 and GH30 include endo-1,4- β -xylanases of both bacterial and fungal origin that have been used to enzymatically release feruloylated arabinoxylo-oligosaccharides from various biomass substrates [19–21] (but GH5 endo-1,4- β -xylanases appear unable to accommodate feruloylated substitutions in the active site [9]).

Based on the tenet that the right combination of FAE and endo-1,4- β -xylanase enzymes would enable selective release of FA from BSG via synergistic cooperation, the individual action of three different FAEs, and the cooperative action between these FAEs and each of two different

types of endo-1,4- β -xylanases was evaluated on two types of BSG, with the objective of achieving effective and selective liberation of high yields of ferulic acid from BSG. The FAEs used in the study were selected based on previous work regarding FA release efficiency and robustness [17, 19], and the endo-1,4- β -xylanases were selected to assess enzymes from different GH families known to have different attack preferences depending on the xylan backbone substitutions [9].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Substrate

BSGs were supplied by two industrial breweries located in Copenhagen, Denmark, namely Carlsberg and ABBA, of which ABBA is a microbrewery. The material was collected fresh from the breweries and stored frozen until its use in the laboratory. Before use, the BSG was washed with deionized, Millipore filtered water until neutral pH and then dried at 80 °C overnight. The resulting material was milled (IKA® MF10 basic microfine grinder, IKA Staufen, Germany), sifted to a particle size of ≤ 0.4 mm and stored until required for processing or analysis.

2.2. Enzymes

The FAEs, *AnFae1* (UniProtKB-A2QSY5), *AoFae1* (UniProtKB-A2QSY5) and *HiFae* originating from *Aspergillus niger* CBS 513.88 (*An*), *Aspergillus oryzae* RIB40 (*Ao*), and *Humicola insolens* (*Hi*), respectively (Table 1), had been recombinantly expressed in *Aspergillus oryzae* MT3568an amdS [22] and purified to electrophoretic purity using hydrophobic interaction and ion exchange chromatography, and were obtained from Novozymes A/S (Bagsværd, Denmark) (The enzymes were the same as those used in [19]). The endo-1,4- β -xylanases were Shearzyme®, an *Aspergillus aculeatus* derived enzyme [23] which is

Table 1

Information about the fungally derived FAEs employed in the study; all were recombinantly expressed in *A. oryzae* [22] and had been purified to electrophoretic purity (the enzymes were a gift from Novozymes A/S, Denmark).

Enzymes	<i>AnFae1</i>	<i>AoFae1</i>	<i>HiFae</i>
Source organism	<i>A. niger</i> CBS 513.88	<i>A. oryzae</i> RIB40	<i>Humicola insolens</i>
Accession number	UniProtKB-A2QSY5	UniProtKB-Q2UNW5	(sequence in [19])
Classification (CAZy)	CE1	CE1	Unclassified FAE
Specific activity on methyl ferulate U/ μ M enzyme ^a [19]	235	165	76
Theoretical Mw (kDa)	30.6	30.2	31.6
Catalytic domain	83–225	83–225	34–220
Catalytic Serine Motif Sequence	GHSLG	GHSLG	GFSSG

^a One activity unit (U) is defined as the amount of enzyme required to convert 1 μ M of esterified hydroxycinnamic acid substrate to the corresponding free hydroxycinnamic acid per minute at 25 °C and pH 6.

Fig. 1. Stylized structure of glucuronoarabinoxylan: *trans*-ferulic acid (highlighted in red) is found esterified to arabinose side-chain residues. GH30 endo-1,4- α -xylanase (EC 3.2.1.8) and feruloyl esterases (FAE) (EC 3.1.1.73) catalyze the hydrolysis of bonds indicated by arrows.

heterologously produced in a genetically modified *Aspergillus oryzae* strain, and sold as a commercial GH10 enzyme preparation, which we obtained from Novozymes A/S (Bagsværd, Denmark), and a recombinantly produced bacterial GH30 endo-1,4- β -xylanase originating from *Dickeya chrysanthemi*, cloned and expressed as described previously [21].

2.3. Chemical extraction of ferulic acid from BSG

The total FA content from BSG was assessed by a classic two-step alkaline treatment as described previously [24]. In brief, BSG (1% w/v) was treated with 2 M NaOH for 1 h under agitation at room temperature, after which the pH was adjusted to pH < 2 with HCl, and the sample was centrifuged for 10 min at 10,000 g. The supernatant was saved, and the pellet saponified with 2 M NaOH. After the saponification, the pH was adjusted to pH < 2 with HCl, the supernatant from the first saponification was added, and the total supernatant was extracted by three rounds of ethyl acetate extraction [24]. Finally, the extracts were pooled and dried at 20 °C for 72 h. Before HPLC-MS analysis (described below), samples were re-dissolved in water.

2.4. Individual enzyme treatments

The effects of the FAEs (*AnFae1*, *AoFae1*, and *HiFae*), Shearzyme® and the GH30 enzyme were studied individually for their ability to liberate FA from BSG. In addition, treatments with combinations of each FAE with each of the endo-1,4- β -xylanases (Shearzyme® and GH30) were investigated to assess any possible synergies on the FA release from the BSG substrates. Before adding any enzyme, BSG (10 mg mL⁻¹) was pre-incubated in 10 mM sodium acetate, pH 6 for 15 min. Then, each substrate was treated with each of the enzymes at 30 °C during continuous shaking (in closed Eppendorf tubes) at 1000 rpm using thermomixers (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany), and samples were taken at 0.5, 1, 2, 6, 24 and 48 h.

The dosages used were 1 μ M for the individual FAEs and Shearzyme®, and 0.1 μ M for GH30. Immediately upon sampling, insoluble substrate was removed by centrifugation at 14,000 \times g for 3 min, and the activity of the enzymes was halted by heating the supernatants at 100 °C for 20 min. After cooling on ice, the FA release was analyzed quantitatively by HPLC-MS as described below.

2.5. Combined treatments, kinetics assay

BSG (substrate levels varying from 1 to 25 mg mL⁻¹) was pre-incubated in 10 mM sodium acetate, pH 6, at 30 °C under agitation for 15 min in Eppendorf tubes. Each sample was treated individually with *AnFae1* (1 or 2 μ M), Shearzyme® (1 μ M), or GH30 (0.1 μ M) or with the combination *AnFae1*-Shearzyme® or *AnFae1*-GH30 for 30 min under agitation (1000 rpm). The FA release was assessed as described above in the section Individual enzyme treatments.

2.6. HPLC-MS analysis of ferulic acid from BSG

The Dionex UltiMate 3000 UHPLC system, equipped with a Diode Array Detector (DAD) and connected to an ion trap (amaZon SL, Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) through an electrospray ionization (ESI) interface (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Sunnyvale CA, U.S.A.), was utilized to quantify the FA content of the samples. The separation was accomplished on 5 μ L injection volumes of samples using an ODS-L Optimal column (250 \times 2.1 mm, 5 μ m) from Capital HPLC Ltd. (Broxburn, Scotland, U.K.) with an elution flow rate of 0.2 mL min⁻¹, a column temperature of 40 °C, and gradient elution using a mobile phase of 0.1% formic acid (eluent A) and acetonitrile (eluent B) [18]. The electrospray was operated in negative scan mode at a capillary voltage of 4.5 kV; end plate offset of 0.5 kV; nebulizer pressure of 3.0 bar, and dry gas temperature of 280 °C, and the detector was operated in multiple reaction

monitoring (MRM) mode using a target mass of 400 *m/z*; total sample runtime was 45 min including re-equilibration, and the Bruker Compass Data Analysis v.5.2 program was used for data handling and peak integrations, all as previously described [18]. Retention time was confirmed by authenticated standards, and quantification of FA relied on direct correlation between the MS intensity peak area and a standard curve of FA [18].

2.7. Quantification of reducing sugars

The dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) reducing sugars method was used to estimate the total concentration of reducing sugars after enzymatic treatment of BSG. All chemicals used were analytical grade, purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). The DNS reagent contained 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (10 g L⁻¹), sodium potassium tartrate (30 g L⁻¹) and NaOH (16 g L⁻¹). Xylose calibration curves in the range of 0.002 – 1.00 mg mL⁻¹ were used for quantification.

The samples and the DNS reagent were added into wells in 96-well microplates and the color reagent reaction was developed by heating at 100 °C for 10 min using a thermomixer (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The absorbance plate was then measured at λ = 540 nm using a BioTek Epoch2 microplate reader (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA).

2.8. Statistics

All data are based on triplicate experiments and are expressed as average \pm standard deviation. Statistical analyses were done by one-way ANOVA and data comparison using Tukey's model. Statistical significance of the results was established at *p* < 0.05. Data processing was done using Microsoft Excel® (Redmond, WA, USA) and SPSS version 22.0® (IBM Corp., NY, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. FA content in BSG

The total FA levels in the BSG samples from Carlsberg and ABBA were similar and ranged from 0.35% to 0.4% by weight (dry matter), equivalent to FA concentrations of 3.5–4.0 mg g⁻¹ (Table 2). These levels were in complete agreement with those reported by Bartolomé et al. [17] for spent barley grain and were considered the theoretical maximum in relation to determining the efficiency of FA release from BSG by the different enzymatic treatments being studied. The *p*-coumaric acid levels in the BSG samples were ~10% of the FA levels (Table 2) and were not considered further.

3.2. FA release by the individual FAE enzymes

The highest releases of FA catalyzed by the action of the individual FAEs ranged from 7.5% to 10% of the total FA (with the total defined as alkali-extractable FA, Table 2) and the release yields were similar for the two BSG substrates (Fig. 2). The maximum levels were achieved already after 6 h of hydrolysis, and although the net yields obtained with the

Table 2

Content of ferulic acid and *p*-coumaric acid in BSG, given as % weight dry matter, from two different breweries Carlsberg and Abba (evaluated by alkaline extraction). Data are given as average values of triplicate determinations (\pm s. d.); different superscript letters a, b means that levels of the two different hydroxycinnamic acids differ significantly in the BSG per brewery (*p* < 0.05), different superscript letters x, y means that the levels of the same hydroxycinnamic acid differ significantly across the two brewery samples (*p* < 0.05).

	Carlsberg	ABBA
Ferulic acid	0.35% (\pm 0.05) ^{a,x}	0.40% (\pm 0.06) ^{a,x}
<i>p</i> -coumaric acid	0.04% (\pm 0.01) ^{b,x}	0.05% (\pm 0.01) ^{b,x}

Fig. 2. Time course of ferulic acid release (relative to total content) by enzymatic treatment with *AnFae1*, *HiFae*, *AoFae1*, GH30 and Shearzyme® alone. Data are given as yield in weight percentage of the total (alkaline extractable) level of FA in the BSG. A) BSG from Carlsberg's brewery, B) BSG from ABBA's brewery.

HiFae treatment appeared slightly higher than those of the two *Aspergillus* derived enzymes, *AnFae1* and *AoFae1*, there was no profound difference in the yields obtained by the individual FAEs, despite their different activities on methyl ferulate (Table 1). Surprisingly, the individual endo-1,4- β -xylanase treatments liberated 1–3% of the FA after prolonged treatment, highest for Shearzyme® (Fig. 2). Both the GH30 and the GH10 Shearzyme® endo-1,4- β -xylanase were recombinantly produced, and the GH30 was extensively purified prior to use. For arabinoxylan hydrolysis, the Shearzyme® endo-1,4- β -xylanase is known to accommodate substitutions in the +1 active site subsite, leading to oligomers with terminally substituted xylose moieties at the non-reducing end [23]. The data suggest that the *A. oryzae* production strain may produce low levels of FAE as undeclared side-activity, which manifests as FA release during prolonged treatment.

3.3. FA release by combined treatments with FAE and endo-1,4- β -xylanase

When a FAE and an endo-1,4- β -xylanase, *i.e.*, GH30 or Shearzyme®, were combined, a large increase in FA release was obtained, demonstrating the synergistic action of the two types of enzyme activity (Fig. 3), which we ascribe to the FAE being far more active on the solubilized arabinoxylan than on the corresponding insoluble arabinoxylan in the BSG. This comprehension is in complete agreement with data obtained for FAE action on other types of soluble versus insoluble fractions of (glucurono)arabinoxylan substrates [19,25]. The

combination of the *AnFae1* and GH30 endo-1,4- β -xylanase resulted in particularly high yields (~80%) after 24 h of treatment, and there was no pronounced difference in the yields obtained from the BSG from the two breweries. As evident from the progress curves (Fig. 3), more than 85% of the total yield of the combined *AnFae1* and GH30 treatment was obtained already after 6 h. With the other enzyme combinations, a maximum of 45% yield of FA was obtained after 6–24 h (Fig. 3).

HiFae and *AoFae1* were also able to release FA from the different BSG when they were combined with GH30, but at lower efficiency than the *AnFae1*-GH30 combination (Fig. 3).

The combinations with Shearzyme® were generally less efficient than those with the GH30 (despite the lower protein dosage of the GH30), except for the combination *AnFae1* and Shearzyme® that gave FA release on par with that of the *AoFae1* and GH30 treatment (Fig. 3). GH30 endo-1,4- β -xylanases, especially some of those belonging to subfamily 7 and 8, *i.e.*, GH30_7 and GH30_8, are known to be specific for GlcA-substituted xylan regions in arabinoxylans [9]. The *D. chrysanthemi* GH30 enzyme used here has been reported to even require the presence of a α -1,2-linked (4-O-methyl)-glucuronic acid substitution at the –2 position in its active site for action as the interaction of the enzyme with the 4-O-methyl-glucuronic acid residue has been suggested to ensure proper distortion of the xylan chain for hydrolysis [26]. To our knowledge, the arabinoxylan in barley grains, and hence in BSG, has not been described as extensively GlcA-substituted. The early detailed analyses and the methods used on arabinoxylans from barley and barley malt mainly targeted the neutral monosaccharide composition (mainly

Fig. 3. Time course of ferulic acid release by enzymatic treatment with the pairwise combinations of each FAE, *AnFae1*, *HiFae*, *AoFae1* and each endo-1,4- β -xylanase, GH30 and Shearzyme®, respectively. Data are given as yields in weight percentage of the total (alkaline extractable) FA in the BSG. A) BSG from Carlsberg's brewery, B) BSG from ABBA's brewery.

arabinose, xylose, galactose, and glucose), and present 4-O-methyl-glucuronic acid may have escaped the chromatographical analyses (e.g. [17,27,28]), or were obtained only as “uronic acids” and interpreted as pectic substances, as in [29]. More recent analyses using immunochromatography technology to monitor the fate of the barley polysaccharides during the beer brewing process, have confirmed the significant presence of feruloylated polysaccharides in the spent grain fraction [30]. The microarray analysis, which is considered highly sensitive, was also able to track the presence of glucuronoxylan in barley malt samples using a monoclonal antibody having “glucuronoxylan” specificity [30], but the microarray analysis did not pick up any presence of methyl-GlcA-substituted arabinoxylan in the BSG (the microarray data were reported as heatmap values, and the analyses do not provide absolute levels, but relative abundance of the particular epitope in a comparative set of samples). Nevertheless, the data for the barley malt [30], together with our recent data with the *D. chrysanthemi* GH30 enzyme on corn bran [19,21] provided the basis for our hypothesis that the GH30 might help solubilize the arabinoxylan from BSG. Acetyl groups were not assessed in the microarray analysis and to the best of our knowledge, acetyl groups have not been considered in other studies on barley arabinoxylan either [e.g. 27–29]. On this basis it appears unlikely that the superior effectivity of the *AnFae1* and GH30 combination was a result of a hitherto unknown high level of methyl-GlcA-substituted arabinoxylan in the BSG substrates. Rather, despite the eminent original structure-function analysis of the GH30 enzyme action on a (4-O-methyl)-glucuronoyl substituted xylotriose tetramer [26] it seems more likely that the GH30 enzyme can catalyze the hydrolysis of β -1,4-bonds in (glucurono)arabinoxylan without requiring the α -1,2-linked (4-O-methyl)-glucuronic acid at the -2 position. Recent docking analysis [21] of the *D. chrysanthemi* GH30 enzyme's action on highly substituted corn arabinoxylan (modeling

differences on the ligand bound at the active site of the protein crystal structure with a ligand, i.e. PDB 2Y24) thus opens the possibility that there may be room in the active site for the xylosyl in $+1$ to carry substitutions. Based on the results obtained here, it is thus possible that effective scissile bond attack may not necessarily require the fitting of a (4-O-methyl)-glucuronic acid at the -2 position if other substitutions on xylosyls in the xylan chain may be able to foster proper substrate distortion for effective scissile bond attack by the enzyme. In addition, the recombinantly expressed GH30 enzyme was carefully purified using affinity chromatography and might for this reason have a significantly higher enzyme activity towards arabinoxylan than Shearzyme®, even at the 10x lower molar protein dosage used. Based on the results obtained, the concentration of *AnFae1* FAE was increased, and the enzymatic release was studied on the BSGs from the two different breweries, maintaining the same operating conditions. By increasing the enzyme dosage of *AnFae1* from 1 to 2 μ M an increase in the recovery of FA in the beginning of the treatment was observed (Fig. 4), and the maximal levels were achieved already within 30–60 min of treatment. The data infer that a maximum yield of FA of $\sim 85\%$ of the total FA could be achieved when the FAE enzyme dosage was increased, and thus demonstrate that high yields of FA can be released from BSG within a short treatment of 30–60 min at mild reaction conditions using the right combination and dosages of a feruloyl esterase (*AnFAE1*) and an endo-1,4- β -xylanase (GH30). Extending the incubation time to 6 h did not enhance yields (Fig. 4), neither did further extension of the reaction time (data not shown). The canonical esterase activity of FAEs is hydrolytic ester bond cleavage to release of ferulic acid; the original classification of FAEs into functional types called Type A–D included the ability to release 5–5' diferulic acid [31]. The *AnFae1*, originally classified as Type A [31], has recently been shown to catalyze release of diferulic acids from solubilized corn bran [19]. Although BSG may contain low levels of diferulic

Fig. 4. Time course of product release during enzymatic treatment with *AnFae1* at two different dosages (1 or 2 μM , LD or HD) and GH30, Shearzyme®, respectively, and the pairwise combinations. Data are given as yields in weight percentage of the total (alkaline extractable) level of FA in the BSG. A) BSG from Carlsberg's brewery, B) BSG from ABBA's brewery.

Fig. 5. Enzyme kinetics given as rates of enzymatic FA release ($\mu\text{g FA} \times (\text{mL} \cdot \text{min})^{-1}$) on different substrate concentrations of BSG (mg mL^{-1}) by *AnFae1*, GH30, Shearzyme® and the respective pairwise combined treatments, *AnFae1* + GH30 and *AnFae1* + Shearzyme® after a reaction time of 30 min. A: Low *AnFae1* dosage (1 μM) on BSG from Carlsberg's brewery; B: High *AnFae1* dosage (2 μM) on BSG from Carlsberg's brewery; C: Low *AnFae1* dosage (1 μM) on BSG from Abba's brewery; D: High *AnFae1* dosage (2 μM) on BSG from Abba's brewery.

acid cross-links, the levels are considered too low for targeted release for valorization and were not considered in the present work; any enzymatic release would likely require a too long treatment time, and eventually provide only trace concentrations of the diferulic acids in the hydrolysate. A short reaction time is generally attractive in order to enhance the feasibility and thus lower the reaction tank size for desirable production yields.

3.4. Kinetics of the enzymatic extraction

The reaction studies (Figs. 3–4) were accomplished on substrate concentrations of BSG of 1% w/w, equivalent to 10 mg mL⁻¹. A set of substrate saturation reactions were done to assess the rate of FA release as a function of BSG substrate concentration; when rates were defined after 30 min of reaction, the highly elevated rates obtained with the *AnFae1* + GH30 combination were evident (Fig. 5). Maximal rates of FA release of 12 μg (mL · min)⁻¹ were achieved at BSG concentrations of 18–20 mg mL⁻¹, with the maximum release rates being highest for the BSG from the Carlsberg brewery (maximum release rates from the BSG from the ABBA brewery were 10 μg (mL · min)⁻¹, Fig. 5). Although the combinations with the high *AnFae1* dosage gave faster release at the lower substrate concentrations for both BSG substrates, Fig. 5 B and D, the maximal release rates achieved at BSG levels of 18–20 mg mL⁻¹ did not differ between the high and low *AnFae1* dosages in combination with GH30 (Fig. 5). Table 3 shows the values (%) of synergistic action obtained between the difference of the yield (%) from the enzymatic hydrolysis of the theoretical sum of the enzymes and the observed combination of them for the FA recovery. Indeed, the highest yield was found between the combination *AnFae1*(H.D) and GH30. However, when *AnFae1* was studied at low dosage (1 μM), higher yields were also observed. The enzyme synergies are likely a result of the endo-1,4-β-xylanases activity solubilizing feruloylated arabinoxylan on which the *AnFae1* works much faster than on the corresponding insoluble substrate.

3.5. Polysaccharide degradation

Liberation of reducing sugars was determined in the final extracts obtained after the enzymatic treatments (Fig. 6). The results obtained showed a similar tendency as the FA release results, particularly corroborating the highest release by the combination *AnFae1* and GH30

Table 3

Synergistic action between the enzymes given as the %yield of the theoretically maximal (alkaline extractable) FA release from BSG; data are averages of the yields on the two brewery samples (1% w/v, i.e. 10 mg mL⁻¹) after 30 min of enzyme treatment. The hypothetical sum is the added levels of FA release achieved by the respective individual enzyme treatments; the Combination indicated the yields obtained after each type of combined FAE + endo-1,4-β-xylanase treatment; and Synergy is calculated as the extent of synergy calculated as the difference in yields [Combination – Hypothetical sum] of the corresponding treatments. Different superscript letters a, b and i, ii, iii means different yields within the data in a column (p<0.05), different superscript letters x, y means that the levels differ significantly between the corresponding Hypothetical Sum data and Combination data in a row (p<0.05).

Enzymes	Hypothetical Sum (% yield)	Combination (% yield)	Synergy (% yield)
<i>AnFae1</i> LD ^a + GH30	4.6 ^{b,y}	26.9 ^{ii,x}	22.3
<i>AnFae1</i> LD + Shearzyme®	4.1 ^{b,y}	9.1 ^{iii,x}	5.0
<i>AnFae1</i> HD ^b + GH30	7.6 ^{a,y}	67.4 ^{i,x}	59.8
<i>AnFae1</i> HD + Shearzyme®	7.1 ^{a,y}	11.4 ^{iii,x}	4.3

^a LD: Low Dosage (1 μM).

^b HD: High Dosage (2 μM).

(Fig. 6). Interestingly, the treatments with each of the endo-1,4-β-xylanases alone gave similar release rates, even with the GH30 enzyme being dosed at 10x lower molar dosage than the GH10, i.e. at 0.1 μM and 1 μM, respectively. The rates of bond cleavage on the two BSG substrates were also similar, achieving a maximum rate of ~2·10⁻⁴ μmol (mL · min)⁻¹ per endo-1,4-β-xylanase within the tested BSG substrate range, and a maximum of ~7·10⁻⁴ μmol (mL · min)⁻¹ with the synergistic enzyme combination of *AnFae1* and GH30, measured as reducing ends in molar xylose equivalents (Fig. 6). The synergistic effect thus enabled increased liberation of reducing sugars, confirming that the enzymatic synergism for the FA release is consistent with polysaccharide degradation.

3.6. Industrial ferulic acid purification considerations

There are currently no standardized practices or protocols for large scale purification of FA, e.g. from aqueous hydrolysates as those obtained here. The first step would be to separate the insoluble BSG remaining after enzymatic treatment, this can be done by centrifugation, typically by use of a continuous centrifugal separator depending on the process scale. Depending on the purity requirement of FA, further purification may be accomplished by use of microporous polymeric adsorbents, e.g. Amberlite XAD resins, which has long been known to effectively separate polyphenols, including hydroxycinnamates, from aqueous extracts by adsorption-desorption [32]. XAD resins are available in a range of mesh sizes and polarities; the more non-polar work effectively by hydrophobic interaction as originally demonstrated for removal of humic matter sediments from water [32], flavonoids from aqueous extracts [33], and recently for purification of natural aqueous phenol extracts from sugarcane straw [34]. FA is considered thermostable, but the phenol may oxidize, and shielding from light and excessive oxygen exposure would be required. Although the FA content only constitutes 0.35–0.4% by weight of BSG (Table 1), the economical revenue on FA is potentially high. FA is on the market in a range of products for facial skin care/anti-aging use, that sell at 50 US\$ per 10 mL at concentrations of 0.5% ferulic acid usually supplemented with 10–15% ascorbic acid as a combination antioxidant.

4. Conclusion

The ability of the three different fungally derived feruloyl esterases (*HiFae*, *AnFae1* and *AoFae1*) and two different types of endo-1,4-β-xylanases (a bacterial GH30 and a GH10 enzyme (Shearzyme®) to catalyze release of FA from BSG from two different breweries was studied. A maximum yield of ~10% of the available FA was released after 6 h treatment with the individual FAEs. A combination treatment with an FAE and an endo-1,4-β-xylanase produced up to 70% yield of FA after 6 h, and up to 80% yield after 24 h with the best result being achieved with the *AnFae1* and the GH30 endo-1,4-β-xylanase; doubling of the *AnFae1* dosage in combination with the GH30 endo-1,4-β-xylanase liberated ~85% of the available FA in 30–60 min from both of the BSG samples. The profound effect of the GH30 in the combination indicates that the *D. chrysanthemi* GH30 enzyme may not have a strict requirement for positioning of a (4-O-methyl)-glucuronic acid substitution at the –2 position in its active site, as the available data on barley kernel arabinoxylan do not suggest that this type of arabinoxylan, and thus the arabinoxylan in BSG, is heavily substituted with (4-O-methyl)-glucuronic acid. Nevertheless, the potent synergistic effect observed between the designed combination of *AnFae1* and the bacterial GH30 paves the way for a new type of upgrading approach to obtain ferulic acid efficiently and selectively from BSG in a sustainable way.

Statement of novelty

This work shows for the first time the use of a targeted combination of two enzymes that act synergistically to maximize release of ferulic acid from brewer's spent grain, thus presenting a new approach for

Fig. 6. Release rates of reducing sugars (as μmoles of xylose equivalents) after enzymatic treatment by *AnFae1*, GH30, Shearzyme® displaying the synergistic action between combinations of *AnFae1*+GH30 and *AnFae1*+Shearzyme®, respectively, after enzymatic reaction of 30 min on BSG from the two different breweries, Carlsberg and ABBA, respectively. Data are given as rates of solubilization of reducing sugars (in $\mu\text{mol xylose} \cdot (\text{mL}\cdot\text{min})^{-1}$) for different substrate concentrations [S] $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of BSG.

valorization of brewer's spent grain – the most abundant byproduct from beer brewing.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pedro Martins: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Paula Bucci:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Visualization. **Anne S. Meyer:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Raul Muñoz:** Writing – review & editing, Resources.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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